

Growth Points

Focusing on transplants

Transplant Systems - authorised user of the name Lannen Plant Systems in Australia and New Zealand

Improved rooting of cuttings in Plantek trays - aeration the answer

Growers are reporting excellent rooting of cuttings when set into Plantek trays. Not only are rooting percentages improving, but also the speed of root initiation and growth.

Side slots incorporated into the trays are intended to prune the lateral root system. A side benefit of this cell construction is the extra air which can penetrate the cell. The result is elimination of the stagnant zone in the centre of the cell - precisely the point where cuttings are most likely to be inserted.

Air movement into the cell of a seedling tray is clearly superior where air can move in through the side slots. This extra aeration eliminates the zone of stagnant air frequently found in cells without side slots. The base of cuttings is typically inserted into this zone of stagnant air, thus hindering rooting.

Hydrangea slips rooted in Plantek 81F trays.

During rooting, cuttings need a high air content in the rooting medium. Traditional practices recommend using a sharp river sand, or incorporating something into the peat mix to increase the air filled porosity. A reduction in water-holding capacity is typical of these ingredients. The alternative is to use a container which allows increased air movement into the cell. Plantek F trays with side slots are now being used for faster and more vigorous rooting, shortening the time until the plant material is ready for transplanting.

Bedding plants - 14 days from plug to sale

An editorial by Vic Ball in the September 1994 issue of Grower Talks should be of particular interest to retailers of bedding plants. In the article, Vic predicts that the 14-day flat will be the future of bedding plant production.

The trend in bedding plant sales is to have fewer, larger seedlings in a punnet, and to have the plants in bud, with at least some colour showing. The main seasons for bedding plant sales tend to be quite short, so any advance in being able to push punnets through to retail sales during this period is an advantage.

The 14-day flat is based on a large plug size. The American 144 cell tray is approximately mid-way in size between the Plantek 144 and 256 trays. Lannen has recognised this need and has introduced a tray of 192 cells.

Essentially only two classes of bedding plant are needed for retail plant scheduling. These are the fast

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plants such as impatiens, petunias and marigolds, requiring down to 14 days to finish from big plugs. Slow plants, such as begonias, may require up to 21 days to finish from big plugs. Clearly, big plugs offer the advantage of much simplified plant scheduling.

Greiling Farms, Wisconsin, USA expect large plugs to become far more widely used. This will be at

the expense of the small 800-size. The popularity of this small size grew during the recession years, it makes sense that economic recovery should change the criterion of nursery efficiency. Whether local nurseries will make the change remains to be seen, but early indicators are that some have already taken advantage of larger plug seedlings.

Radiata planting season

Radiata pines are generally planted during late winter and perhaps into early spring. Experience indicates that this is the optimum planting period to cope with the restrictions imposed by bare rooted plants, but is it the optimum period for optimal initial establishment?

Soil temperatures are known to have a marked effect on root growth. Root initiation and elongation in radiata pines is greatly retarded when soil temperatures drop below 14°C. Poor root extension after planting in winter results in water stress in the shoots of seedlings, which would be aggravated by low soil moisture. In extreme cases, the plants will die.

It is known that radiata pines grow actively throughout the year. However, seasonal flushes of growth do occur. The spring shoot flush is probably the most obvious. For all plants, root growth is normally very poor when rapid shoot growth occurs.

Recent studies of radiata root growth patterns confirm that the most active root growth occurs during early to mid winter, with a marked decrease in growth

in spring. While the current planting period is unlikely to change for bare rooted plants because of climatic constraints, containerised stock is probably best planted just before this period of active root growth. Plants will have time to establish lateral roots into the surrounding soil before soil temperatures and the spring shoot flush restricts new root growth.

This is a most fortunate coincidence of timing for the setting of radiata cuttings. Operating on the traditional late winter planting programme, nurseries setting a new crop of cuttings run into a severe overlap in terms of growing space. The new season cuttings need to be set before the previous crop has been planted! Fortunately, if the optimum planting time for containerised stock proves to be the early to mid winter period, this timing conflict is neatly resolved.

Extremely dry soils, and the likelihood of severe early frosts will limit the potential for autumn planting. Moderate irrigation immediately after planting will improve survival.

Vegetable seedlings - what difference does the tray make?

Vegetable seedlings have to be robust to withstand the rigours of handling. A long narrow root plug is easily damaged during handling, particularly where the roots

Poor root form on plants when the seedlings are kept too long in the seedling tray. This effect is made far worse where the seedling tray has rounded edges to the cells.

have not been able to fill the cell properly. Further damage can occur where the stems are broken away from the base of the root plug when lifting individual seedlings from the tray during planting. This is easily seen a few days after planting, since the leaves cannot be sustained by the few roots that might be planted with them. Counting the number of root plugs remaining in the tray after planting is a tell tale guide to the effectiveness of the tray.

Vegetable growers, also, have not generally considered the shape of the root system to be particularly important. This is in stark contrast to the concerns expressed by foresters and, increasingly, by landscapers. Container design is known to have a profound impact on the performance of plantation trees and perennial plants in a landscape. A similar effect occurs with flower and vegetable crops.

Single harvest vegetable crops are probably the easiest crops to check the effect of poor root form on

yield. Crops such as lettuce, cabbage and broccoli are generally established using seedlings to obtain plant uniformity. A single harvest is the ideal, but seldom achieved. However, having to go over the crop more than four times is a clear indication that something is happening to reduce plant uniformity.

Since these crops are highly bred, often F₁ hybrids, their genetic uniformity will be high. If the nursery has done its job correctly, the seedlings will be uniform. Lack of uniformity must therefore be introduced during the planting operation. Where field factors play a role, this is generally quite clear in the pattern of harvest, such as delayed growth in cold, wet depressions, or poor vigour where weeds have not been controlled.

The role of the root plug and handling of the seedlings is seldom considered when investigating

New dual seeding conveyor

This system has been introduced to eliminate the possibility of incorrect seed placement in the dibbled cells when pre-filled cell trays are indexed under a row dibble bar and then proceed to the seeding position while remaining on a common conveyor belt. The new conveyor incorporates two belts independently operated. The pre-filled trays are first placed on the dibble conveyor and dibbled automatically, row by row. The trays continue to be indexed forward, and are discharged from the dibble conveyor to be received by the seeding conveyor. This conveyor indexes forward, allowing seeding to take place row by row under the discharge tubes.

The new dual conveyor shown as installed at a commercial grower in Werribee, Victoria. Independent indexing of the trays for both the dibble and seeding functions eliminates the problems introduced by trays slipping on the belt. Contact Lannen Plant Systems for details.

vegetable yields. Cell trays that induce roots to circle are quite common. Permanent damage to the root system is linked to the shape of the cell as well as the age of the seedling. To complicate matters, this appears to be physiological age, and not simply chronological age.

It is more difficult to establish whether poor yield has been induced by poor handling during planting. Slightly dry root plugs can reduce yields markedly. Combine this with a degree of root distortion during planting, and yields can be depressed by as much as 30%.

Current recommendations are to select a cell tray with square-formed cells and ample drainage to improve aeration. With effective air-pruning and a smooth, tapered cell wall, the root plugs are easily extracted without damage. Lannen 144 trays have been scientifically designed to achieve these objectives.

The Gleason FF41DE flat filler is an excellent choice for many nurseries, shown here linked to a Lannen automatic tray feeder for Lannen 144 trays, and a Hamilton Natural Seeder for general vegetable seedling propagation.

Nelson Vegetable Seedling Nursery Achieves One-Man Tray Filling and Seed Sowing Operation

Rob Conning has only one employee attending to his continuous, in-line tray filling and seed sowing facility.

Rob has installed a Lannen automatic tray feeder which releases Lannen 144 trays automatically to his Gleason tray filling machine. In effect, Rob has a continuous row of trays, with no gaps between, moving through his system, achieving an uninterrupted flow of cells being presented to his Hamilton Natural seeder and seed covering unit. After seed covering, the trays proceed through a watering tunnel, and are transported to a germination area.

Large container stock

Large containerised stock is necessary for both landscape and horticultural applications. Should one start out in the large container directly, or is there an advantage to increasing the container size progressively during propagation?

The main factors in favour of repotting are a saving of space in the nursery and less capital loss should some plants die in the nursery. Offsetting this is the high labour cost.

Renewed growth following potting up is probably more related to the new charge of nutrients becoming available, or even to better aeration in the new potting mix for new root growth. Variable results in trials suggest that this is not necessarily an important factor in initial pot choice.

Of more concern in the propagation programme must be the ability to cull at an early stage and thus save on space, pots and mix. This is particularly important where poor germination or root strike occurs. Rooting of liners and plug production of seedlings are now common practices in nurseries producing plants for all purposes. A variation is the increasingly popular option for forestry and tree crops of lining-out small containerised plants to produce an even stand of plants destined to be lifted as bare root plants.

Whether the plants in small containers are to be repotted or lined out depends on the end requirement. Advantages of container stock are, in particular, a longer planting season with reduced labour requirement, higher plant yield from valuable seed or cutting material, and more dependable production results.

Plantek forestry trays show growth

Containers are being used extensively around the world for tree propagation. Most plantation sites are showing an increase in numbers of plants started in containers. New Zealand foresters, for many years using the bare root method almost exclusively, are now also discovering that containers can make sense.

What is the essential difference between side slot containers and other plastic containers? The side slots allow the lateral roots to be pruned, thus ensuring the regeneration of a natural root form after planting. Most plastic containers used for plantation forestry incorporate vertical ridges to prevent roots circling. The addition of lateral root pruning is necessary to prevent a root cage

forming where all the root tips point downwards. These downward pointing roots have been implicated in predisposing plants to windthrow and poor growth, although early survival and height growth can be excellent.

Lateral root pruning is achieved in bare root nurseries by physically cutting the roots. In containers, only chemical and air pruning have proven practical methods of lateral root pruning. Air pruning is the preferred method where hard plastic trays are used. The side slots are incorporated in the design and therefore do not entail any on-going costs.

What evidence is there that New Zealand foresters are accepting containerised plants? Probably the best indication comes from nurseries deciding to increase their production of containerised plants. They would certainly not be increasing production if the plants did not sell. A rough estimate is some 12 million plants will be planted out this season from containers, up from about 8 million last year. Early indications are that next year will see production of at least 15 million containerised plants.

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LANNEN PLANT SYSTEMS

PO Box 29-074	PO Box 295
CHRISTCHURCH	BERWICK
New Zealand	Victoria 3806
	Australia
03-348 2824	fax 059-989 020
03-348 2823	telephone 059-985 398

Information required:

Name:

Address:

Phone: Fax:

Growth Points is published by Transplant Systems Limited, PO Box 29-074, Christchurch, New Zealand.

Tel: 03-348-2823, Fax: 03-348-2824.

Editor: Warrick Nelson

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